

REVIEW ARTICLE

REVOLUTIONIZING AGE ESTIMATION: TECHNIQUES OF LONG BONE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

In this review we have discussed age estimation from long bones involves a multi-dimensional approach, considering various techniques and factors. Ongoing research and the integration of non-invasive techniques hold promise for improving accuracy in age estimation. Age estimation at death using information from long bones involves employing various techniques that depend on the age of the remains and the available anatomical areas for analysis. Histological analysis of long bones shows potential for age estimation, but further research is needed to enhance its accuracy. Epiphyseal union and diaphyseal length have been extensively studied in certain populations, although anthropologists should examine the specific population in their region to determine the age of epiphyseal union for good comparison. In cases involving fetal remains, priority is given to assessing long bone lengths. Radiography and direct measurement, with appropriate data and conversion methodologies, are important approaches. Non-invasive techniques like Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and machine learning algorithms show promise, providing reliable and valid results without using ionizing radiation. During childhood, long-bone diaphyseal lengths and measurements of other bones remain crucial for age determination.

Keywords: Skeletal remains, age determination, long bones, forensic anthropology.

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INTRODUCTION

Forensic anthropology is a branch of physical anthropology that applies scientific methods to assist in legal investigations. It primarily deals with cases involving the examination of skeletal remains or bone samples. In order to identify a bone, it is crucial for a forensic anthropologist to determine its nature (i.e., whether it is a bone) and, if it is indeed a bone, to ascertain whether it belongs to a human or a non-human organism. This process involves several steps, including bone identification, followed by age and gender estimation.

Long bones are characterized by their elongated shape, where their length exceeds their width. These bones are segmented into three distinct parts along their elongated axis, with two of them occurring in pairs. The middle section is called the diaphysis, while on either side of it are the metaphyses. Finally, at the ends of the bone, there are the epiphyses. The shaft of the bone is formed by the diaphysis. (Francillon-Vieillot et al., 1990)

Estimating age from long bones commonly involves assessing physiological age of them and correlating it with chronological age. The specific techniques employed vary depending on the available sample and the age range of the individual being analyzed. Different techniques may be specific to particular bones or parts of bones, and the methods applicable for estimating age in fetal remains are not relevant for adults.

The metaphysis, located in the elongated region of the bone, undergoes elongation through a process known as endochondral ossification. During this process, cartilage is gradually replaced by bone, as supported by studies conducted by (Amizuka et al., 2012). Ossification initiates in the diaphysis, as observed by (Francillon-Vieillot et al., 1990). Consequently, the diaphysis accumulates the highest amount of cortical deposit, (Sander & Tüeckmantel, 2003).

To examine bone thickening, researchers commonly analyze cross-sections in the diaphysis, often focusing on the mid-shaft.

Physical methods for age estimation are not highly accurate, and tooth eruption is typically complete by the age of 16. However, epiphyseal fusion of long bones is a relatively consistent and reliable method for estimating age up to 22 years. (Patel et al., 2011)

The complex processes of growth, maturation, and aging lead to changes in long bones that can be utilized for estimating age at death. These changes encompass increases in external dimensions, the appearance and fusion of epiphyses and other ossification centers, remodelling, bone loss, arthritic changes, and shifts in chemical composition. Information about growth, epiphyseal development, and fusion is particularly useful for estimating age in immature individuals and has even been applied to predict future growth in liv-

ing individuals. The remaining processes provide valuable information for estimating age at death in adults. (Ubelaker & Khosrowshahi, 2019)

Study Of Age Of Union For Epiphyses Of The Long Bones

Bone growth initiates during fetal development within the mother's womb. At the time of birth, the skeleton is incompletely formed, with many bones still in the process of formation. Throughout childhood, bone components continue to grow and fuse together. This fusion process typically concludes by the age of 17 to 25 years, signifying the cessation of normal growth.

In immature skeletons, certain separate bone components are referred to as epiphyses, located at the ends of the long bones in the arms and legs. Epiphyses serve as growth centers and are prominently visible at the extremities of long bones.

At birth, these ends consist mainly of cartilage, a resilient and flexible type of connective tissue, with internal bone centers beginning to form. As a child grows, the bone shafts lengthen, gradually replacing the cartilaginous epiphyses with bone tissue.

Throughout the years of growth, a layer of cartilage known as the growth plate separates each epiphysis from the bone shaft. During the teenage years, the epiphyses fuse with the main bone shafts as the cartilage growth plate is fully replaced by bone. This fusion process generally occurs slightly earlier in females compared to males.

By examining the stages of epiphyseal fusion in various bones and comparing them to standard growth tables, it is possible to estimate a person's age. (Sharma, 1974)

The fusion of the epiphysis at the distal end of the tibia typically occurs in the majority of cases around the ages of 16 to 17 years for both males and females. The earliest observed fusion was found to take place at 16 years of age for both genders. However, it is important to note that the findings regarding the age of earliest fusion do not align conclusively with any other existing studies for comparison. (Priya, 2017)

A prospective study was conducted in 2009-2010 at the Forensic Medicine Department of B. J. Medical College in Ahmedabad, India. The study involved 104 subjects of both sexes, aged between 15 and 21 years, with known ages. The researchers focused on observing the epiphyseal fusion at the lower ends of the radius and ulna, which progressed bilaterally and symmetrically. They found that the fusion process typically began between the ages of 16 and 18 and completed by the end of 20 years.

Additionally, they noted that the fusion of the ulna occurred earlier than that of the radius, and females tended to show earlier fusion compared to males.

These findings highlight the reliability and usefulness of observing epiphyseal fusion as a method for age

estimation, particularly in the absence of proper birth registration. Understanding the timing and progression of epiphyseal fusion can provide valuable insights into the age of an individual, assisting in various legal and forensic contexts. (Patel et al., 2011).

The growth pattern of long bones in juvenile Eskimo and Aleut skeletons mirrors that of present-day Eskimo and Aleut populations. These populations experience a significant growth spurt before adolescence, with females showing particularly intense growth during this period. However, after the age of 14, male long bones surpass those of females in terms of length. The distinctive body proportions observed in adult Eskimo and Aleut individuals are established early in childhood. Compared to individuals of Caucasian descent, Eskimos and Aleuts generally have shorter bones at all ages. Notably, the difference in forearm and lower leg length between Eskimos, Aleuts, and Caucasians appears to become more pronounced during adolescence. (Y*Edynak, 1976).

The radiological method of studying epiphyses has certain evident advantages over the purely anatomical. The examinations are made in the living subject and therefore the age can be indubitably established, as also considering the fact that the subject is normal and does not suffer from any of the nutritional or endocrine diseases. (Paterson, 1929).

These observations, which align with similar findings, have strengthened the belief in the theory that various factors such as geographic-climatic conditions, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and dietary habits contribute to the fusion of epiphysis with age. These shared influences seem to play a significant role in the timing and progression of epiphyseal fusion. By recognizing the impact of these factors, we can further refine age estimation techniques and improve our understanding of skeletal development in different populations. (Tirpude et al., 2014).

Study Of Internal Bone Structure

When studying cancellous tissue, the humerus and femur are primarily considered, with the humerus being given priority. The methods employed involve radiological examination of bones and the examination of longitudinal sections to analyze the resorption pattern of cancellous tissue.

In the case of the humerus, the proximal end of the medullary cavity takes on a cone shape. Over a span of 40-50 years, the tip of the cone gradually reaches the surgical neck of the bone, and by 60-75 years, it continues to ascend towards the epiphyseal line.

In the study of cancellous tissue, microscopic analysis focuses on cortical elements such as osteons, osteon fragments, lamellar bones, and non-Haversian canals. By examining these elements, it becomes possible to estimate age within a margin of 5 years. One method involves counting the number of osteons in a cross-section of bone, although this technique is not considered accurate or reliable on its own (Erol et al., 2016).

A study examined microscopic age changes in human cortical bone by analyzing the number of osteones, osteon fragments, non-Haversian canals, and the percentage of lamellar bone in the outer third of the cortex. Ground sections from the mid-shaft of the femur, tibia, and fibula were used.

Age graphs were created based on 126 specimens spanning from birth to 95 years. Regression analysis revealed that the best correlation with age was observed in the number of osteon fragments in the fibula ($\rho = 9.74$). Using a regression formula based on this factor, the age could be estimated within a $\pm$ ten-year range of the actual age with 95% accuracy.

An alternative method involved using specific profile chart to estimate age from the age change graphs. When tested on an additional 56 specimens, 87.3% of the estimates

Table1: Age of Union for Epiphyses of Some of the Long Bones(Sharma, 1974)

Long bone type	Female initial union (years)	Male initial union (years)	Female/Male Union complete (years)
Proximal humerus (upper arm)	14 - 20	14 - 21	18 - 25
Distal radius (outer forearm)	16 - 19	16 - 20	18 - 22
Femur head (thigh)	13 - 17	15 - 18	18 - 20
Distal femur	14 - 17	14 - 19	18 - 22
Proximal tibia (shin bone)	14 - 17	15 - 19	18 - 23
Distal tibia	14 - 16	14 - 18	18 - 20

Table2: The important ossification centers in long bones and their fusion(Sharma, 1974)

Humerus (upper end) • Head • Greater tubercle • Lesser tubercle	1 year. All 3 unite at 6 years 3 years 5 years	18 years 4-5 years with head 5-7 years with greater tubercle
Humerus (Lower end) • Medial Epicondyle • Capitulum • Trochlea • Lateral Epicondyle	5-6 years 1 year 9-10 years 10-12 years	Capitulum, trochlea & lateral epicondyle form conjoint tendon at 14 years, unites with shaft at 15 years Medial epicondyle unites at 16 years
Radius • Upper end • Lower end	5-6 years 1-2 years	15-16 years 18-19 years
Ulna • Upper end • Lower end • Head 1st metacarpal • Head other metacarpals	8-9 years 5-6 years 2 years 1½ to 2½ years	16-17 years 18-19 years 15-17 years 15-19 years
Femur (Upper end) • Head • Greater trochanter • Lesser trochanter Femur (Lower end)	1 year 4 years 14 years 9-month IUL	17-18 years 17 years 15-17 years 17-18 years
Tibia • Upper end • Lower end	10-11 years 14-15 years	14-15 years 17-18 years

were within ± five years of the actual age, and all estimates were within ± ten years.

It was concluded that significant microscopic age changes occur in the cortex of major long bones in the leg, allowing for accurate age estimation across the entire lifespan from birth to 95 years. This method is applicable to fragmented, incomplete, and eroded skeletal remains since it focuses on the mid-shafts of leg bones.(Kerley, 1965).

Estimating Age From Diaphyseal Length.

The preferred method for estimating the age of archaeological sub-adult skeletons is through dental examination. However, in cases where dental records are unavailable, age estimation can be performed using other indicators such as epiphyseal union, skeletal elements, or diaphyseal lengths. Currently, there is a lack of specific data on age estimation based on diaphyseal lengths for medieval Danish sub-adults.

In a study, a sample of 58 Danish archaeological sub-adults ranging from approximately six to twenty-one years old was examined.

The samples were age-graded using two dental methods: **Haavikko and Ubelaker**. Regression formulas were

developed to estimate age based on diaphyseal lengths, both for individual long bones and combinations of upper and lower long bones. The findings of this study suggest that reasonable age estimation results can be obtained for Danish sub-adults using the developed regression formulas.

Furthermore, the Danish data was compared to data from a different archaeological sample and a modern sample. The comparison revealed that the modern data consistently indicated lower ages compared to the archaeological sample, with the difference increasing until reaching a maximum of nearly five years and six months. However, when comparing the archaeological data to the findings of this study, it was observed that the growth profiles intersected at 12.5 years, with the archaeological data showing a maximum age difference of two years and three months lower before the intersection point, and a maximum difference of three years and four months higher after the intersection point.(Primeau et al., 2012).

A study employed regression and classical calibration techniques to establish a relationship between age and diaphyseal length of six long bones. The sample comprised 184 individuals (72 females and 112 males) below the age of 13, selected from Portuguese and English skeletal collec-

Table3: Comparison of age of proximal end of humerus in various regions and races(Tirpude et al., 2014)

TABLE II: Comparison of Age of Epiphyseal fusion in Proximal end of Humerus			
S.N.	Researcher	Region	Age of fusion
			Female
1)	Paterson (1926)	England	18
2)	Davies and Parson (1927)	England	18-20
3)	Flecker (1932)	Australia	17
4)	Pillai (1936)	Madras	17-18
5)	Galstaun (1937)	Bengal	14-16
6)	Krogman (1960)	USA	18-19
7)	Reddy KSN (1973)	Andhra Pradesh	17-18
8)	Sahana S.N (1986)	Bengal	18
9)	Knight B(1996)	UK	14-21
10)	Saini et al (2005)	Rajasthan	17-18
11)	Agrawal Anil (2006)	Delhi	17
12)	Memon et al (2006-08)	Pakistan	16-17
13)	Cardoso Hugo (2008)	Spain	20
14)	Schaefer M.C.(2008)	Bosnia	-
15)	Pimple et al (2013)	Mumbai	17-18
16)	Present Study	Central India	17-18

tions with known age and sex. Age estimation models were developed using classical calibration for each of the six long bones, separately for each sex, combined sexes, and for the entire sample. Additionally, the sample was divided into two subsamples at the age of 2 years for analysis.

Comparisons between inverse and classical calibration methods revealed a systematic bias in age estimations obtained from inverse calibration. The models based on classical calibration, particularly using the length of the femur, provided the most accurate age estimates. The accuracy of age estimation was higher in the male subsample and for individuals under the age of 2 years.

These findings, along with a comparison to previously published methods, caution against using inverse calibration as a technique for developing age estimation methods, particularly for the immature skeleton. The study highlights the importance of using classical calibration techniques and underscores the accuracy and reliability of the femur length

for age estimation purposes.(Cardoso et al., 2014)

New standards have been proposed for estimating the age of juvenile individuals in the ancient Maya civilization. These standards take into account variations in stature and limb proportions observed in Mesoamerican groups, which differ from the prehistoric North American groups used to develop existing standards. To establish these new standards, a study analyzed data from 75 juvenile individuals in the protohistoric Maya series from Tipu, Belize. By measuring the lengths of the femur, humerus, and tibia, regression equations were created to predict the age of dental development, and these equations demonstrated a strong fit and statistical significance.

Furthermore, when the equations were applied to diaphyseal lengths from other Mesoamerican populations, the results supported the validity of using these standards across different Mesoamerican groups.(Danforth et al., 2009)

Table4: Regression formulae for age estimation (L is the length of corresponding long bone in cm) (Primeau et al., 2012)

Bone	N	Formula	Standard error of estimate (years)	p-value	R ² -value
Clavicle	38	(L × 1.968) – 9.596	± 1.875	> 0.001	0.832
Humerus	52	(L × 0.787) – 6.944	± 1.255	> 0.001	0.904
Ulna	33	(L × 0.983) – 7.180	± 1.348	> 0.001	0.894
Radius	29	(L × 1.058) – 6.728	± 1.149	> 0.001	0.917
Femur	37	(L × 0.565) – 6.901	± 1.265	> 0.001	0.920
Tibia	26	(L × 0.639) – 5.458	± 1.114	> 0.001	0.930
Fibula	16	(L × 0.675) – 5.827	± 1.558	> 0.001	0.779
Hum + fem	34	(L × 0.331) – 7.087	± 1.269	> 0.001	0.913
Hum + uln	31	(L × 0.445) – 7.356	± 1.266	> 0.001	0.908
Hum + rad	27	(L × 0.452) – 6.896	± 1.113	> 0.001	0.923
Fem + tib	23	(L × 0.300) – 6.451	± 1.103	> 0.001	0.936
Fem + fib	13	(L × 0.322) – 7.266	± 1.559	> 0.001	0.817
Rad + tib	17	(L × 0.394) – 5.673	± 1.100	> 0.001	0.905

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Machines Learning For Age Estimation

Age estimation is a crucial aspect of forensic medicine when determining the age of individuals lacking valid legal documentation. Traditional methods used for age estimation are labor-intensive, subjective, and often involve radiation exposure. Recently, non-invasive approaches using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) have shown promise by correlating growth plate ossification in long bones with chronological age, particularly in young subjects.

However, there is a need for automated and user-independent methods to reliably assess age in large datasets. This study aimed to develop a fully automated and computer-based method for age estimation using 3D knee MRIs and machine learning.

The proposed solution consisted of three components: image pre-processing, bone segmentation, and age estimation. The dataset included 185 coronal and 404 sagittal MR volumes from Caucasian male subjects aged between 13 and 21 years.

The best result obtained through a fivefold cross-validation approach showed a mean absolute error of 0.67 ± 0.49 years in age regression. For classification with an age limit of 18 years, the method achieved an accuracy of 90.9%, sensitivity of 88.6%, and specificity of 94.2%. This was achieved by combining convolutional neural networks and tree-based machine learning algorithms.

The study demonstrated the potential of deep learning in age estimation, and further improvements can be made by training the models on larger and more diverse datasets

for age estimation and its application in forensic medicine (Kaur & Moza, 2023; Mauer et al., 2021; Moza et al., 2023; Verma et al., 2023).

The researchers developed a novel staging system using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to evaluate the maturation of the growth plate in the knee joint. Age estimation was done in living individuals by retrospectively reviewing 290 MRI scans of the knee from individuals aged 10 to 30 years (138 males, 152 females).

The researchers defined five distinct MRI stages to assess the level of maturation in the distal femoral and proximal tibial epiphyses. They found that the intra-observer agreement was excellent, indicating high reliability, and the inter-observer agreement was good, indicating reasonable validity of the MRI staging system.

The changes in the growth plates (proximal tibial or distal femoral) were significantly associated with age in both males and females ($p < 0.001$).

The results were consistent with existing data on skeletal maturation of the knee, showing earlier maturation in females compared to males and earlier maturation of the proximal tibial epiphysis compared to the distal femoral epiphysis. However, the researchers emphasize the need for larger studies to further validate these findings.(Dedouit et al., 2012; Moza et al., 2024).

A study aimed to evaluate different methods for determining the age of fetal remains, including traditional and expedited approaches. Due to their infrequent occurrence, the discovery of fresh, decomposing, distorted, or skeletal foetuses presents a challenge for forensic pathologists who need to estimate the age of the foetus in relation to viability.

Dentists primarily focus on the mineralization of primary molars when dealing with decomposed complete

or isolated fetal remains, while anthropologists employ long bone measurements and consider other indicators of skeletal maturity to estimate age.

They found

1. The most effective technique for obtaining fetal tooth buds and long bones involved dissecting the developing tooth buds and macerating the long bones.
2. Metric analysis was used to estimate age based on tooth buds and long bones, and the findings were compared and correlated.
3. Statistically significant differences were observed between the known age and dental age, as well as between dental age and long bone age. Although the difference between known age and long bone age was not statistically significant, this may be attributed to a type II error due to the small sample size.
4. Additionally, a new staging technique for central incisors was developed specifically for fetuses younger than 26 weeks, complementing the existing molar staging system introduced by Kraus and Jordan in 1965. (Crumpton et al., 2023)

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) used to determine the fusion of the distal femoral and proximal tibial epiphyses as an indicator of age. The study aimed to specifically establish reliable markers for identifying the 14th, 16th, and 18th years of life. Research was done with a total of 658 German volunteers aged between 12 and 24 years were scanned using a 3.0 T MR scanner.

A T1 turbo spin-echo sequence was employed to accurately depict the bone anatomy. Various statistical measures such as minimum, maximum, mean $\pm$ standard deviation, and median with lower and upper quartiles were calculated. The agreement between different observers and within the same observer was assessed using Cohen's kappa coefficient. Sex-related differences were analyzed for statistical significance using the Mann-Whitney U test ($p < 0.05$, two-sided, exact). (Ottow et al., 2017)

The results indicated that the fusion of both epiphyses occurred prior to the 18th year of life. The Mann-Whitney U test demonstrated significant sex-related differences in most stages of fusion. The intra observer agreement (κ femur 0.961; tibia 0.971) and interobserver agreement (κ femur 0.941; tibia 0.951) were found to be very good for both epiphyses. (Ottow et al., 2017)

In conclusion, based on the closest-to-bone MRI analysis, it is possible to determine the 14th and 16th years of life in both sexes using the fusion of the distal femoral and proximal tibial epiphyses. However, the completion of the 18th year of life cannot be solely determined by bony fusion.

Therefore, MRI can be thought of an appropriate method for forensic age estimation from the knee. The process offers information about the ossification process without the need for ionizing radiation. This method enables the identification of the 14th and 16th years of life. However,

relying solely on bony fusion is inadequate for determining legal majority. (Kaur et al., 2023; Ottow et al., 2017).

CONCLUSION

Various techniques are employed to estimate age at death using information from long bones. The accuracy and effectiveness of these techniques depend on the age of the remains being examined and the specific anatomical areas available for analysis. To determine the age at death, it is essential to consider all available evidence comprehensively. Study of histological analysis of long bones can be done but it needs to be researched further for more accuracy. Epiphyseal union and diaphyseal length are have been researched for a decade, however, every anthropologist is required to study the age of union of epiphyses of the population of their region.

When dealing with fetal remains, priority is given to assessing the lengths of long bones.

Other measurable bones are also considered, taking into account available data or established measurement standards. Whether measurements are obtained through radiography or direct measurement of isolated bones, it is crucial to employ appropriate data and conversion methodologies. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and machine algorithms are emerging non-invasive techniques that have been successfully used to assess age from long bones. They scan bones with non-ionizing radiation and form results with good reliability and validity.

In age determination during childhood, long-bone diaphyseal lengths and measurements of other bones continue to play a significant role. Additionally, measurements of soft tissues can provide valuable insights. As individuals progress through adolescence, the appearance, growth, and union of epiphyses become important indicators, particularly in cases involving soft tissue remains. Furthermore, as individuals reach adolescence, information regarding sex and population variation becomes relevant and should be considered if available for age estimation (Baccino et al., 1999; Priya, 2017; Villa & Lynnerup, 2014).

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Conflict of interest

NONE

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